

Position Paper on Nicotine Misperceptions and Tobacco Harm Reduction: Physician Perspectives from a Middle East Round Table Meeting

Author Names and Affiliations:

Mohammad Fawzi Katranji¹, Mohamed Hassan Ahmed², Adel Khattab³, Raghad Hashim⁴, Mansoor Habib⁵

¹Al Zahra Private Hospital, Dubai,UAE

² Sheikh Khalifa Medical City, Ajman, UAE

³ Ain Shams Faculty of Medicine, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt

⁴Department of Basic Medical and Dental Sciences, Ajman University, Ajman, UAE

⁵Soulware Coaching, Dubai, UAE

Corresponding Author: Mansoor Habib

Emailid: drmansoor.habib2026@gmail.com

Abstract:

Tobacco use in the Middle East remains a major public health challenge, shaped by the continued dominance of cigarette smoking alongside the widespread use of traditional tobacco products (TTPs) such as waterpipe and midwakh. Although the scientific evidence clearly demonstrates that the primary drivers of smoking-related disease are the toxicants produced during combustion rather than nicotine itself, this distinction is poorly understood. Misperceptions about nicotine persist among the general population and healthcare professionals alike, influencing clinical decision-making, public attitudes, and policy approaches, and potentially limiting engagement with effective cessation and harm reduction strategies.

This position paper draws on multidisciplinary expert discussions held during a regional roundtable meeting, supported by a review of the contemporary scientific literature. Clinicians from family medicine, pulmonology, cardiology, psychiatry, and dentistry deliberated on prevailing nicotine misperceptions, regional patterns of tobacco use, and the ethical, clinical, and operational considerations surrounding tobacco harm reduction (THR) in Middle Eastern healthcare settings.

Participants noted that while smoking cessation services are available in many settings, THR is rarely integrated in a structured or transparent manner. Uncertainty regarding relative risk, concerns about professional responsibility, and the absence of clear clinical guidance were identified as factors that reduce clinician confidence in discussing potentially reduced risk alternatives with patients who are unable or unwilling to quit. International experience including Sweden's long-standing use of non-combustible nicotine products was examined to illustrate how risk-proportionate regulation and informed clinical engagement can contribute to meaningful reductions in smoking

prevalence and smoking-related disease burden, effectively reshaping national public health profiles.

While complete cessation remains the preferred public health objective, the expert panel agreed that THR can serve as a pragmatic and patient-centred complement to existing tobacco control strategies for adult smokers who would otherwise continue to smoke. Addressing nicotine misperceptions through targeted professional education, clear and balanced risk communication, and the development of region-specific evidence was seen as essential for responsible implementation. This paper offers evidence-based recommendations for clinicians, policymakers, public health communicators, and researchers aimed at strengthening the ethical and effective integration of harm reduction approaches within the broader tobacco control framework in the Middle East.

Key words: Alternative nicotine products; Combustible tobacco; E-cigarettes; Smokeless tobacco; Waterpipes

Introduction

Tobacco use remains a major contributor to preventable disease and mortality worldwide, accounting for more than seven million deaths annually and substantially increasing the burden of cardiovascular disease, chronic respiratory illness and cancer.¹ Tobacco use is also associated with reduced physical, mental and social functioning, contributing to poorer overall health outcomes and substantial economic costs related to healthcare utilisation and productivity losses.¹ Cigarette smoking continues to be the dominant form of tobacco consumption globally.¹ The WHO estimates a decline in smoking rates across many high-income countries like the United States and the United Kingdom, while smoking remains high or continues to increase in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).¹⁻³

Against this global backdrop, the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region faces a complex and evolving tobacco landscape. In addition to cigarette smoking, the widespread use of waterpipe tobacco, often perceived as a less harmful or a more socially acceptable alternative, adds materially to the regional disease burden contributing significantly to cardiovascular disease, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and multiple cancers.^{1,3,4} Evidence consistently shows that most of tobacco-attributable harm is driven by toxicants generated during combustion rather than by nicotine itself.⁵⁻⁸ This distinction is increasingly relevant to contemporary public health discourse, particularly in the context of evolving nicotine delivery systems and harm-reduction approaches.⁵⁻⁸

Global surveys indicate that many adults including physicians incorrectly believe nicotine to be the primary cause of smoking-related cancers.⁵⁻⁸ Such misperceptions have important public health implications, as they are associated with reduced uptake of evidence-based nicotine replacement therapies and lower acceptance of non-

combustible nicotine products with substantially reduced toxicant exposure profiles, including heated tobacco products, electronic vapour products and oral nicotine pouches.⁵ In the Middle Eastern context, where tobacco control messaging has historically emphasised abstinence without clear differentiation between nicotine delivery systems, these factors may inadvertently constrain smokers' engagement with risk-reduction pathways.⁹ Nicotine misperceptions may be further reinforced by additional structural and sociocultural factors, including limited awareness of cessation options, stigma associated with tobacco dependence, doubts regarding the effectiveness of cessation services and gendered social norms that influence help-seeking behaviour. Collectively, these misunderstandings complicate both conventional tobacco control efforts and the implementation of complimentary THR strategies.

Given the region's high and diverse tobacco use prevalence, transparent communication of relative risks, particularly the distinction between the harms of combustion and the pharmacological role of nicotine, may play a critical role in strengthening cessation efforts, improving the acceptance of harm-reduction tools, and ultimately reducing smoking-related morbidity and mortality across the Middle East. This position paper aims to provide a comprehensive examination of tobacco use, persistent nicotine misperceptions, and tobacco control strategies in the Middle East, with a focus on the evolving role of THR within clinical and public health frameworks. The main objectives are to:

- Map the current tobacco landscape by analysing the prevalence, patterns and emerging trends in tobacco consumption, while highlighting the cultural and demographic factors that shape these behaviours across the region;
- Highlight the persistence and impact of nicotine misperceptions among the public and healthcare professionals, and to clarify the differential risk profiles of

alternative nicotine products such as heated tobacco products, vapour products, and oral nicotine pouches within the context of evidence-based harm reduction;

- Identify the clinical and operational challenges faced by healthcare professionals in supporting adult smokers who are unwilling or unable to quit, including gaps in cessation services, unclear referral pathways, and limited integration of THR within existing clinical frameworks;
- Position THR as a pragmatic extension of current cessation and tobacco control strategies, informed by insights from regional clinicians and supported by global scientific evidence;
- Emphasise the need for region-specific evidence generation, including systematic data collection, surveillance and evaluation of lower-risk nicotine products to inform clinical guidance and public health policy; and
- Encourage constructive collaboration between healthcare systems, regulatory authorities, academic institutions, and industry stakeholders to ensure responsible, transparent and scientifically grounded THR implementation guided by an evidence-based approach.

Round Table Overview

The roundtable convened a multidisciplinary, evidence-informed dialogue on nicotine misperceptions and THR in the Middle East with the aim of translating global evidence into regionally relevant approaches.

The selection of participating physician healthcare advisors (PHAs) for the roundtable meeting was conducted using a purposive sampling approach to ensure multidisciplinary representation, regional diversity, and a balanced range of perspectives on harm

reduction strategies. Physicians were identified based on their clinical background, publication record, conference presentations and experience in clinical management of tobacco-related public health issues. Special emphasis was placed on identifying PHAs working in pulmonary and respiratory health, given their direct involvement in managing smoking-related diseases; however the specialists from related fields such as family medicine, cardiology, psychiatry and dentistry were also included to reflect the broad spectrum of medical disciplines associated with tobacco-related health consequences. National and institutional diversity was also considered to capture insights from across the United Arab Emirates and the broader Middle East region. Among the identified experts, the PHA with the most extensive publication record and highest level of professional activity served as Chair for the meeting. The Chair was responsible for moderating the discussion, facilitating balanced participation among attendees, and ensuring that the deliberations remained focused on the predefined objectives. This structured approach ensured a credible, scientifically grounded and multidisciplinary dialogue on THR practices, clinical considerations and policy implications within the regional healthcare context.

Discussions addressed the regional burden of tobacco use, including TTPs such as shisha and midwakh, persistent nicotine-risk misperceptions, and the potential role of THR as a complement to conventional cessation strategies, moving beyond the limitations of the 'quit or die' paradigm. Sweden's THR experience was reviewed to consider its relevance within regional, cultural, regulatory and healthcare contexts. The meeting further examined the role of healthcare providers in smoking cessation, identifying gaps in training and system-level support, and explored structured transition pathways for smokers, highlighting ethical considerations and the need for personalised, patient-centred care. These evidence sources helped validate and complement

expert opinions, and foster open, evidence-informed discussion rather than to establish a formal consensus, and this position paper synthesises these insights into a structured narrative on prevailing regional perspectives on THR. It is intended as a directional reference rather than an official guideline.

Global Context: Distinguishing Nicotine Risks from Combustible Tobacco Harms

A substantial body of evidence has established that the major health harms of smoking arise from tobacco combustion rather than nicotine itself.^{8,10–12} Nevertheless, misperceptions about nicotine remain common among the public and healthcare professionals, with surveys indicating frequent misattribution of smoking-related cancers to nicotine.^{5–7}

A key contributor to this misunderstanding is limited awareness on cigarette composition, wherein nicotine is often perceived as the dominant harmful constituent because it is the most recognisable and pharmacologically active component.⁵ Inconsistent public health messaging and media narratives further reinforce this confusion by conflating nicotine exposure with the harms of smoking.^{7,8} International discussions, including those highlighted during a panel discussion at the eighth Summit on Tobacco Harm Reduction: *Novel Products, Research & Policy*, held in Athens 2025, have underscored the urgency of correcting misinformation that equates nicotine per se with smoking-related toxicity.¹³ When nicotine's actual risk profile is misunderstood, healthcare providers may hesitate to engage in evidence-based THR discussions, and smokers may be less willing to transition away from combustible products.⁵ Such misunderstandings have appreciable clinical and policy consequences, as they limit the

acceptance of harm-reduction strategies and discourage the consideration of potentially lower-risk alternatives for smokers who struggle to quit combustible tobacco.

From a mechanistic perspective, the health burden of smoking is driven primarily by the products of tobacco combustion. The 'burning' of tobacco generates tar, carbon monoxide, formaldehyde, and numerous carcinogens that are primarily responsible for smoking-related morbidity and mortality.^{8,10} On the other hand, Nicotine is an alkaloid found in the tobacco and acts as a potent psychoactive compound primarily through its interaction with the nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs) in the central and peripheral nervous systems.¹² Upon inhalation, nicotine rapidly crosses the blood–brain barrier, reaching the brain within seconds and stimulating dopaminergic pathways involved in reward and reinforcement, which underpins the development of nicotine dependence.¹⁴ Repeated stimulation of these pathways leads to neuroadaptations, including receptor upregulation and altered neurotransmitter release, resulting in tolerance and withdrawal symptoms upon cessation, thereby sustaining continued use.¹⁵

Beyond its role in dependence, nicotine exerts a range of transient physiological effects, including increased heart rate, cardiac contractility and increased blood pressure.^{10,15} Its effects vary by dose and mode of administration, with acute exposure shown to enhance attention, reaction time and cognitive performance, while repeated exposure leads to neuroadaptations that manifest as tolerance and dependence.¹⁵ Interestingly, emerging evidence also suggests that nicotine may have potential neuroprotective effects, particularly in conditions like Parkinson's disease,¹⁶ although such findings remain inconclusive and do not justify its use outside controlled medical contexts. Importantly, contrary to widespread belief, most tobacco-related diseases such as cancer, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) are not caused by nicotine

itself but by numerous toxic and carcinogenic compounds produced during combustion.^{8,10,12,17}

Correcting the narrative around nicotine can help integrate cessation aids, lower risk profile products, and policy innovations into a coherent framework that ultimately supports a reduction in the tobacco-related disease burden. Harm-reduction approaches advocate for ‘switching rather than quitting’ in populations unable to stop nicotine use completely, using regulated, potentially less harmful alternatives.^{18,19} The U.S. National Academies’ report ‘Clearing the Smoke’ emphasises that non-combusted nicotine delivery systems (such as heated tobacco) present significantly lower toxicant exposure than combustible products.¹²

Recognising this distinction is critical for advancing THR strategies. However, nicotine’s association with addiction/dependence complicates public perception and policymaking. While complete abstinence remains the ideal public health goal, acknowledging relative risks among nicotine delivery systems enables pragmatic strategies that can accelerate reductions in smoking prevalence.¹¹ Regulatory frameworks in countries such as the United Kingdom and the United States of America have integrated harm-reduction models,^{19,20} offering a contrast to more abstinence-focused approaches in regions where nicotine use is still stigmatised.

Understanding the Regional Context

Epidemiology of tobacco use in the Middle East

The Middle East exhibits a distinct epidemiological profile of tobacco use, characterised by a wide range of products, including cigarettes, waterpipes (Hookah), shisha, narghile, midwakh (dokha).^{3,21,22} While cigarettes remain the most prevalent tobacco form; TTPs like waterpipe or midwakh have gained significant traction,

particularly among younger populations and non-smokers or individuals who do not identify as conventional cigarette smokers, raising public health concerns.^{3,22,23} In the UAE, cigarettes account for most of the tobacco use (77.4%), followed by midwakh (15%) and waterpipes (6.8%) (21). Findings from the pilot phase of the United Arab Emirates Healthy Future Study (UAEHFS) further highlight the complexity of tobacco use patterns with approximately one-third of participants reporting regular use of two or more tobacco products (dual or poly-use) with the most common combination being cigarettes alongside midwakh/dokha.²²

At the regional level, the BREATHE study estimated an age- and gender-adjusted smoking prevalence of 31.2% across several Middle East and North Africa (MENA) countries, with substantial variability ranging from 15.3% in Morocco to 53.9% in Lebanon.³ Similarly, National survey from Saudi Arabia demonstrated a prevalence of 15.6% for smoked and 8.6% for smokeless tobacco, with marked gender disparity (men being substantially more likely to use both forms of tobacco than women), and clear socioeconomic gradients across regions.²⁴ For example, the Al-Baha region records significantly higher tobacco usage rates, illustrating regional variability within countries affected by cultural and economic factors.²⁴ The data from the UAE National Health Survey has reported that socio-economic status further influences tobacco behaviour, with lower levels of education and income linked to higher smoking prevalence.^{3,4} Despite this emerging evidence, Khattabh et al. reported that tobacco use remains under-represented in regional surveillance systems and disease burden analyses, owing to the limited tracking of TTPs and underreporting in certain demographic groups.³ This incomplete surveillance obscures the true scale of exposure and complicates efforts to design proportionate, evidence-based interventions.

The cultural acceptance and social normalisation of products such as midwakh and shisha contribute to the underestimation of their health risks and to lower stigma compared with cigarette smoking, reinforcing acceptance among women and facilitating uptake among youth.^{23,25,26} Factors such as product accessibility, peer influence, and increasing visibility across digital and social media platforms are associated with experimentation and increased use among youth.^{27,28} Furthermore, emerging nicotine products (i.e., Nicotine pouches in Saudi Arabia) continue to gain traction, driven by social factors and perceptions of reduced harm.^{4,21,29} Taken together, these dynamics highlight how tobacco use in the Middle East is shaped by the interplay of personal, community, environmental and organisational policy factors,³⁰ underscoring the need for culturally sensitive approaches to enhance tobacco control and cessation outcomes.¹⁷

Policy Environment and Public Health Messaging

Tobacco control policies across the Middle East have aligned increasingly with global standards, notably the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (FCTC) and its MPOWER measures.³¹ All six Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) member states (Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, and the United Arab Emirates (UAE)) ratified the WHO FCTC in 2006 (Article 16), which includes a ban on tobacco sales to adolescents.³² Additional measures include monitoring tobacco use, protecting people from second-hand smoke, providing cessation support, warning about tobacco dangers, enforcing advertising bans and raising taxes on tobacco products.³¹ Despite the widespread ratification of the FCTC across Eastern Mediterranean Region (EMR) countries, implementation remains partial, and enforcement is uneven.³³ Key challenges include weak monitoring systems, limited institutional capacity, and

inconsistent application of policies across jurisdictions.³³ Several Middle Eastern countries have enacted comprehensive smoke-free laws and bans on tobacco advertising, promotion, and sponsorship, while some, like Saudi Arabia, have adopted plain packaging regulations.³³ Taxation on tobacco products has been effective in reducing consumption; however, it has been unevenly applied across the region and often below WHO-recommended levels.³³

Public health messaging campaigns in the Middle east have mixed reach and impact, with some successes in youth-targeted education and cessation promotion,³¹ yet the prevalence of tobacco users is high. Data gaps and surveillance weakness limit policy adaptation and targeted interventions.³⁴ To accelerate progress towards the WHO's regional goal of a 30% relative reduction in tobacco use, Middle Eastern governments must prioritise multisectoral engagement, strengthen the enforcement of existing laws, improve monitoring systems, and select culturally responsive approaches.³³ Importantly, tobacco control and communication efforts in the region have not sufficiently differentiated between nicotine and the harms arising from tobacco combustion. This lack of risk-proportionate communication not only reinforces persistent nicotine misperceptions but also contributes to confusion regarding the relative harms of cigarettes, TTPs, and non-combustible nicotine alternatives. This may also inadvertently undermine acceptance of evidence-based THR strategies, ultimately preventing adult tobacco users from making fully informed decisions. Ensuring access to accurate, evidence-based information may therefore support informed decision-making and contribute to improved public health profiles.³⁵

Key Themes Emerging from Expert Discussions

Commonly Reported Misperceptions in Clinical and Public Settings

Tobacco harm reduction in the Middle East is shaped by a dual burden of misunderstanding: long standing global misperceptions about nicotine are compounded by regionally specific beliefs surrounding TTPs. Together, these factors can be classified into ethical/cultural, educational and system/policy which continue to influence public behaviour, clinical practice, and policy decision-making across the region (Table 1).

Among the general population, TTPs like hookah (shisha) and midwakh (dokka) are frequently perceived as safer alternatives to conventional cigarettes. Social normalisation of TTPs (e.g. shisha and midwakh) promotes the perception that they are 'natural' or safer than cigarettes.^{30,36,37} Many users believe that water filtration in hookah or the herbal additives mixed in dokha purify the smoke, thus minimising harm.^{36,38-41} Additionally, TTPs carry the misperception of being less-addictive.^{39,42,43} The perception that TTPs relieve stress coupled with their deep socio-cultural embedding further reinforces these misbeliefs.^{30,37,38} Moreover, limited awareness regarding harms associated with second-hand and third-hand smoke exposure continues to influence the public attitude and behaviour across the region.^{36,37,43} Importantly, the misperceptions are not confined to the public. Studies have reported persistent use of TTPs including midwakh among healthcare professionals themselves,³⁸ reflecting gaps in knowledge regarding product composition, toxicant exposure, and relative risk.^{18,38,44} Socio-cultural sensitivities surrounding TTP use, combined with limited training in nicotine science and stepwise THR approaches, further hinder clinicians from openly discussing or recommending potentially reduced-risk alternatives.^{38,44,45} These challenges are compounded by under-representation of TTP use in regional surveillance and research which obscures their actual health impact and restricts evidence-based decision making.^{22,30,43}

Barriers to Combating Misinformation

Clinicians play critical role not only in patient care but also in shaping public health policy frameworks. The limited coverage of nicotine science within medical and allied health curricula, along with insufficient training in THR strategies, leaves many clinicians underinformed about the evolving evidence base, with implications for clinical decision-making.^{18,38,45,46}

At the population level, public health campaigns often fail to differentiate between nicotine and tobacco, reinforcing an ‘all-or-nothing’ perception of risk.^{7,47} Additionally, the scarcity of culturally tailored education campaigns and public communication strategies allows misinformation to circulate unchallenged, hindering progress in evidence-based THR strategies and effective cessation practices.³⁰ Regulatory gaps continue to reinforce misinformation and normalise the use of TTPs across the Middle East.^{48,49} Enforcement of FCTC-aligned public-smoking bans remains inconsistent across the region.^{25,33,48,49} And the portrayal of these products as cultural or social symbols, further entrenches their normalisation and obscures awareness of their composition and associated health risks.^{40,49}

Comparable regulatory deficiencies are prevalent in packaging standards as well. Unlike cigarettes, TTPs and their associated accessories often lack consistent labeling and health warnings.^{25,40} Vendor and seller claims such as midwakh (dokha) being ‘natural,’ or less harmful circulate freely through social media, informal marketing, and peer networks further contributing to consumer misperceptions and uncertainty regarding product-related risks.^{36,40,41} Moreover, the heavy reliance on evidence derived from Western populations limits the contextual relevance and applicability of current THR strategies to local sociocultural and behavioural environments, highlighting the need for regionally grounded research and tailored policy development.^{50,51}

Table 1. Common public and clinical misperceptions as well as the barriers to the misperceptions

S. No.	Public Misperception	Barrier
1	Hookah/midwak are more 'pure' or 'safe' than cigarettes	Ethical/Cultural
2	Hookah/midwakh are less addictive and less harmful than cigarettes	Educational
3	Persistence of misperceptions is reinforced by the lack of clear regulatory guidelines or tobacco control strategies	System/Policy
	Physician misperceptions	
1	Reluctance to discuss or recommend harm reduction alternatives	Ethical/Cultural
2	The health hazards of nicotine are equivalent to those of tobacco combustion	Educational
3	Lack of structured clinical guidelines and regulatory policies limits clinical engagement	System/Policy

Divergent Opinions on Tobacco Harm Reduction

The fundamental premise of THR is to significantly reduce morbidity and mortality in smokers unwilling to quit by switching to non-combustible nicotine products (NCNPs) like heated tobacco products, electronic vapour products, and nicotine pouches.

NCNPs significantly reduce the exposure to toxicants generated by combustible tobacco or TTPs.⁵² They satisfy nicotine cravings and preserve behavioural and social aspects of smoking while reducing exposure to many of the toxicants and carcinogens generated by burning tobacco.⁵² By addressing both nicotine dependence and the behavioural and social dimensions of smoking, NCNPs may offer a pragmatic alternative for smokers for whom conventional cessation approaches have been unsuccessful, while markedly lowering toxicant exposure compared with continued cigarette smoking.^{19,52}

Population-level evidence from countries such as Sweden, the United Kingdom, and Japan has demonstrated encouraging trends, including declines in smoking prevalence, reduced cigarette consumption, increased uptake of NCNPs, and measurable improvements in public health indicators.^{18,52,53} Collectively, these observations suggest that, when appropriately regulated and positioned as substitutes for combustible tobacco, NCNPs can contribute meaningfully to tobacco control efforts by accelerating reductions in smoking prevalence and associated disease burden.¹⁸

At the same time, experts acknowledged that NCNPs are not risk-free. They deliver nicotine that poses specific risks for adolescents, as it may increase the likelihood of sustained nicotine dependence in younger populations.^{37,54} The long-term health effects of NCNPs, such as heated tobacco and nicotine pouches, require further characterisation.^{54,55} A key challenge lies in balancing the appeal of these products to adult smokers with the need to prevent initiation among youth and non-smokers. Robust regulatory surveillance and transparent risk communication are essential to prevent misuse, or dual use of NCNPs that could undermine harm reduction efforts.^{54–56} Ultimately, the success of THR depends on the willingness of adult smokers to fully transition away from combustible products.

Table 2: The divergent opinions on Tobacco Harm Reduction discussed in the round table meeting.

S. No.	Pros of Tobacco Harm Reduction	Cons of Tobacco Harm Reduction
1	Aims to reduce morbidity/mortality in smokers unwilling or unable to quit completely	NCNPs deliver nicotine, which is addictive but not the primary cause of smoking related diseases/cancers
2	Reduces exposure to harmful chemicals generated by the combustion of tobacco	Long-term effects of NCNPs like heated tobacco products and nicotine pouches are unclear
3	NCNPs satisfy nicotine cravings, allows social behaviours while minimizing the exposure to harmful chemicals	Addiction requires balancing product appeal by strict regulatory policies and clear communication
4	Demonstrates positive health impact, decline in smoking rates observed in countries like Sweden, UK, Japan	Success depends on adult smoker acceptance and complete transition away from combustible tobacco

NCNPs. Non-combustible nicotine products

Authors' Interpretation and Position

The panel acknowledged the culturally entrenched nature of tobacco use in the Middle East and the widespread misperceptions regarding the relative risks of combustible cigarettes, TTPs, and NCNPs among both public and healthcare providers. They

emphasised the ethical responsibility of clinicians to separate personal or cultural beliefs from clinical decision-making, reaffirming the need for patient-centred and evidence-driven practice.

Dr. Mansoor Habib

“We need to check our own ego, our own stigma. Are we stigmatized by the topic and avoid opening it? Where do I take my personal versus clinical hat?”

Within this context, the panel advocated THR as a pragmatic adjunct to cessation, particularly for adults unable to quit. This framework recognises that smoking behaviours, dependence levels, comorbidities, and readiness to quit vary substantially across individuals, and therefore requires personalised clinical decision-making rather than a one-size-fits-all model.

Dr. Mohamed Hassan Ahmed

“We need to have criteria... defining those who are in need for harm reduction intervention. It should be restricted and tailored.”

Accordingly, the panel endorsed a stepwise, multi-tiered care pathway that integrates behavioural support, pharmacotherapy, and harm-reduction tools as transitional strategies towards complete abstinence, as illustrated in Figure 1. Central to the harm reduction framework is the concept of a risk continuum, acknowledging that while no nicotine use is without risk, non-combustible nicotine products occupy a substantially lower position on the harm spectrum than combustible cigarettes.⁵⁷ Within this paradigm, heated tobacco products, vapour products, and oral nicotine pouches were acknowledged as potentially lower-risk alternatives when used by adult smokers as

substitutes for combustible tobacco.^{18,57} The validity of the risk continuum approach is further reinforced by population-level evidence from Sweden and other high-income countries, where long-term substitution of cigarettes with snus and other non-combustible nicotine products has coincided with lower smoking prevalence, reduced incidence of smoking-related cancers, and measurable declines in smoking-attributable disease burden, including disability-adjusted life years (DALYs).^{18,20,58}

Participants further highlighted the importance of clinical and health-system level preparedness to support effective THR implementation. They emphasised that clinician confidence in discussing THR can be strengthened through structured training/education in nicotine science, relative product-risk communication, and the practical application of the risk-continuum concept in clinical practice. The panel underscored the importance of standardised clinical guidance, decision-support tools, and clearly defined referral pathways to enable consistent, ethical, and patient-centred THR counselling.^{25,30}

The session concluded with a call for coordinated regional action, advocating collaborative clinician education, policy dialogue, and the systematic integration of harm-reduction approaches within existing healthcare and cessation infrastructures to ensure responsible and evidence-based implementation

Figure 1. Stepwise, multi-tiered clinical pathway integrating cessation and tobacco harm reduction.

Evidence-Based Clarifications: The Sweden Study

‘The Sweden Case Study’, was discussed as an evidence-based example for THR integration within a national tobacco control framework.^{19,58} The discussion focused on Sweden’s experience with the incorporation of NCNPs with a reduced risk profile, particularly snus, and their association with measurable reductions in smoking prevalence and tobacco-related disease burden.⁵⁸ Panellists also noted snus deliver nicotine without combustion or tobacco leaf, thereby markedly reducing exposure to the toxicants responsible for smoking-related disease.¹⁹

While long-term population-level data is still evolving, available toxicological and biomarker studies suggest substantially lower risk profiles compared with combustible cigarettes, reinforcing their potential role within a regulated THR framework for adult smokers who would otherwise continue to smoke.⁵⁷ The Swedish experience was used to illustrate how structured harm-reduction policies, when aligned with cessation efforts and clear public communication, can accelerate decline in smoking and improve population health outcomes.¹⁸

However, panellists emphasised that direct transposition of the Swedish model to Middle Eastern settings requires careful contextualisation. Sweden's approach has largely operated as a primary prevention strategy, whereas THR in the Middle East would predominantly function as secondary prevention strategy for current smokers.¹⁸ Differences in cultural norms, oral hygiene practices, regulatory environments, and public health infrastructure were recognised as important considerations when translating lessons from the Swedish experience. Nonetheless, participants emphasised that the core principles underpinning Sweden's success such as risk-proportionate regulation, clear public communication, and clinician engagement remain highly relevant.²⁰ They underscored that effective THR integration in the Middle East should be accompanied by strengthened health literacy initiatives, targeted clinical training, and clear referral pathways to ensure that NCNPs are used responsibly, appropriately, and within a clearly defined public health framework.

Next Steps and Recommendations for Stakeholders

The round table discussions converged on a clear message: addressing nicotine misperceptions is a prerequisite for the responsible integration of THR into cessation pathways, particularly in the Middle East where cultural norms, TTPs, and regulatory

heterogeneity intersect. The following stakeholder-specific recommendations outline pragmatic actions to translate evidence into practice and to position THR as a complementary strategy for adult smokers who are unable to quit (Table 3).

Academic and Institutional Stakeholders

- *Generate Local Evidence:* Panellists highlighted the need for region-specific, culturally sensitive research to address nicotine misperceptions and build a robust evidence base on the safety, efficacy, and suitability of THR approaches in the Middle East.
- *Support Research-Policy Translation:* Panellists emphasised that locally generated evidence should directly inform policymaking, ensuring responsible THR adoption, clear risk communication and alignment of public health messaging with regional needs.

Policymakers

- *Establish a THR Task Force:* Panellists proposed to create a dedicated, multi-disciplinary task force to coordinate physician engagement, promote credible dialogue and ensure unified communication across the healthcare and regulatory ecosystem regarding THR and alternative nicotine products.

Dr. Mohammad Fawzi Katranji

"Getting a source of information that is reliable and authoritative is probably the most helpful thing... You come up with an authoritative task force that produces a statement. That statement becomes the source for everybody to follow."

- *Engage Key Stakeholders:* Collaboration with the ministries of health, regulatory authorities and international experts was viewed as critical to ensure coherence, sustainability and credibility of THR frameworks. Experts advocated for multi-tiered interventions that combine clinical support, a well-articulated regulatory framework and targeted education to facilitate safer behavioural transitions and long-term cessation outcomes.
- *Gain Deeper Insights into Smoking Cessation Clinics:* Panellists emphasised the necessity to evaluate how existing cessation clinics operate, including their focus areas and patient care models. They called for the creation of national smoking cessation programs that incorporate patient stratification, recognising that smokers are a heterogeneous population with varying levels of tobacco addiction, motivation and readiness to quit with implication of THR strategies when appropriate.

Healthcare Professionals

- *Develop Evidence-based Clinical Guidance:* Panellists called for the formulation of standardised, evidence-based frameworks to counter nicotine misinformation, ensure ethical practice and support consistent THR-related patient counselling.
- *Embed THR in Medical and Continuing Medical Education (CME) Curriculum:* The lack of structured THR training in medical education was recognised as a critical gap. Therefore, panellists emphasised on incorporating clinically led and evidence-based harm reduction concepts into undergraduate and CME program to equip clinicians with the knowledge and confidence to guide patients responsibly.

- *Strengthen Clinical Practice Integration:* Panellists supported the inclusion of THR approaches within clinical care pathways and recommended the establishment of clear referral pathways to ensure patient-centred application in cases where complete cessation is not immediately attainable.

Public Health Communicators

- *Promote Coordinated Education and Awareness:* Panellists discussed the need to collaborate with healthcare professionals, policymakers and institutions to deliver clear and consistent public messaging that distinguishes nicotine from combustion-related harm and clearly articulates the rationale for THR.
- *Strengthen Industry Transparency and Collaboration:* Panellists highlighted the importance of long-term, transparent collaboration with industry to support evidence generation, surveillance, education and capacity-building while maintaining safeguards against undue influence.

Table 3. Stakeholder-specific recommendations and their anticipated impact to support the effective integration of THR in the Middle East.

S. No.	Stakeholder	Recommendations on the next steps	Impact
1	Academic and Institutional Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate local or region-specific evidence on THR and nicotine perceptions • Translate local research into policy and public health guidance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthens the evidence base for THR • Ensures policies reflect regional needs and data
2	Polymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish a multidisciplinary THR Task Force • Align with national and international stakeholders for policy coherence • Develop national cessation programmes with patient stratification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhances coordination and regulatory clarity • Enables scalable, evidence-based THR adoption • Supports personalised and effective cessation services
3	Healthcare Professionals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop standardised clinical guidance for THR counselling • Integrate THR into medical training and CME • Embed THR approaches into clinical care pathways 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improves clinician confidence and counselling consistency • Strengthens patient-centred care
4	Public Health Communicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliver consistent, evidence-based THR messaging. • Enable transparent, responsible industry collaboration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduces nicotine misperceptions. • Builds trust and supports long-term public health education

CME, continuing medical education; THR, tobacco harm reduction

Conclusions

Tobacco use across the Middle East remains shaped by a complex interplay of prevailing cultural norms, dual/poly usage of smoking and TTPs such as midwakh and hookah, and persistent misperceptions regarding nicotine vs smoking-related harm. This heterogeneous landscape poses substantial challenges to conventional tobacco control approaches and continues to limit the effectiveness of cessation efforts, necessitating the implementation of harm-reduction strategies.

Across the round table discussions, panellists consistently identified the misattribution of smoking-related disease to nicotine itself as a critical barrier to inform clinical decision-making, patient engagement and policy development. Panellists agreed that addressing these gaps through structured clinician training, evidence-based guidance and culturally sensitive public education is essential to improve risk communication and support informed choices about alternative lower risk profile nicotine products.

The discussions underscored that, while complete cessation remains the ultimate goal, embedding THR within cessation frameworks provides a realistic, patient-centred approach for smokers who are unable to quit. Panellists also called for balanced, transparent regulations grounded in local evidence to protect youth and non-smokers while enabling adult smoker's access to potentially reduced risk alternatives. Together, these insights highlight a strategic opportunity to align education, clinical practice and policy to dispel nicotine misperceptions, strengthen tobacco control and advance public health priorities across the Middle East.

List of abbreviations: CME, Continuing medical education; DALY, Disability-adjusted life years; FCTC, Framework Convention on Tobacco Control; GCC, Gulf co-operation council; MENA, Middle East and North Africa; NCNP, Non-combustible nicotine

products; PHA, Physician healthcare advisors; THR, Tobacco harm reduction; TTP, Traditional tobacco products

Funding statement: Scientific deliberations were supported by an unrestricted educational grant from British American Tobacco (BAT).

Disclosures: BAT had no role in the conceptualization, content development, data interpretation, or conclusions of this paper. The authors are solely responsible for the views and recommendations expressed which are based on independent scientific analysis and expert consensus.

Competing Interests: The authors have no competing interests to declare.

Author Contributions: All authors actively participated in the roundtable discussions that shaped the concept and direction of this manuscript. The ideas, analyses and interpretations presented emerged from these shared discussions. All authors were involved in writing and critically reviewing the manuscript and approved the final version for publication.

References

1. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/tobacco> Last Accessed 01 March 2026
2. Mathers CD, Loncar D (2006) Projections of global mortality and burden of disease from 2002 to 2030. *PLoS Med* 2006; 3(11): e442.
3. Khattab A, Javaid A, Iraqi G, Alzaabi A, Ben Kheder A, Koniski ML, et al. Smoking habits in the Middle East and North Africa: Results of the BREATHE study. *Respir Med*. 2012;106(suppl 2):S16-S24.
4. Razzak HA, Qawas A, Mujahed M, Harbi A. Prevalence, and Associated Factors of tobacco smoking among adults in the United Arab Emirates; Results from National Health Survey. *J Public Health (Berl.)* 2022; 30, 2039–2046
5. Shi R, Feldman R, Liu J, Clark PI. The Dilemma of Correcting Nicotine Misperceptions: Nicotine Replacement Therapy versus Electronic Cigarettes. *Health Commun*. 2021;36(14):1856–66.
6. Bover Manderski MT, Steinberg MB, Wackowski OA, Singh B, Young WJ, Delnevo CD. Persistent misperceptions about nicotine among us physicians: Results from a randomized survey experiment. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(14):7480.
7. Villanti AC, Byron MJ, Mercincavage M, Pacek LR. Misperceptions of Nicotine and Nicotine Reduction: The Importance of Public Education to Maximize the Benefits of a Nicotine Reduction Standard. *Nicotine Tob Res*. 2019 ;21:S88–90.
8. Hannel T, Wei L, Muhammad-Kah RS, Largo EG, Sarkar M. Modeling the population health impact of accurate and inaccurate perceptions of harm from nicotine. *Harm Reduct J*. 2024 ;21(1):38.
9. Quit tobacco use. Status of tobacco cessation in the Eastern Mediterranean Region. Cairo: WHO Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean; 2024.
10. U.S. Dept. of Health and Human Services. How tobacco smoke causes disease: the biology and behavioral basis for smoking-attributable disease: a report of the Surgeon General. 2010. <http://www.surgeongeneral.gov/library>. Last Accessed 09 January 2025
11. Smith TT, Hatsukami DK, Benowitz NL, Colby SM, McClernon FJ, Strasser AA, et al. Whether to push or pull? Nicotine reduction and non-combusted alternatives - Two strategies for reducing smoking and improving public health. *Prev Med (Baltim)*. 2018; 117:8–14.
12. Stratton KR. Clearing the smoke: assessing the science base for tobacco harm reduction. Institute of Medicine, National Academy Press; 2001. 636 p.

13. Researchers, doctors slam nicotine misconceptions at summit. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/2122396/researchers-doctors-slam-nicotine-misconceptions-at-athens-summit> Last Accessed 06 March 2026
14. Jiloha RC. Biological basis of tobacco addiction: Implications for smoking-cessation treatment. *Indian J Psychiatry*. 2010;52(4):301-307.
15. Benowitz NL. *Nicotine Addiction*. Schwartz RS, editor *N Engl J Med*. 2010; 362(24): 2295-2303.
16. Jung SY, Chun S, Cho E Bin, Han K, Yoo J, Yeo Y, et al. Changes in smoking, alcohol consumption, and the risk of Parkinson's disease. *Front Aging Neurosci*. 2023; 15:1181440.
17. Scherer G, Pluym N, Scherer M. Literature Review on Nicotine's Role in Human Health. *Contrib Tob Nicotine Res*. 2024;33(1):1-111.
18. Yach D, Olson C, Fagerstrom K. Tobacco harm reduction and better treatment could save nearly two million lives in selected countries in the Middle East. Report supported by international and local tobacco harm reduction experts June 2024.
19. Tobacco harm reduction: the potential. In: *Global State of Tobacco Harm Reduction*. Chapter 4; 2023.
20. Hatsukami DK, Carroll DM. Tobacco harm reduction: Past history, current controversies and a proposed approach for the future. *Prev Med*. 2020; 140:106099.
21. Razzak HA, Harbi A, Ahli S. Tobacco smoking prevalence, health risk, and cessation in the UAE. *Oman Med J*. 2020;35(5):e190.
22. Al-Houqani M, Leinberger-Jabari A, Naeemi A Al, Junaibi A Al, Zaabi E Al, Oumeziane N, et al. Patterns of tobacco use in the United Arab Emirates healthy future (UAEHFS) pilot study. *PLoS One*. 2018;13(5):e0198119.
23. Alwardat DM, Saddik B, Sreedharan J. Tobacco smoking habits, attitudes and associated factors among women in the United Arab Emirates. *BMC Public Health*. 2026; 26:54.
24. Al-Hanawi MK, Keetile M. Prevalence and correlates of smoked and smokeless tobacco use in Saudi Arabia: evidence from the 2021 national health survey. *Sci Rep*. 2025;15(1):30841.
25. Maziak W, Nakkash R, Bahelah R, Hussein A, Fanous N, Eissenberg T. Tobacco in the Arab world: Old and new epidemics amidst policy paralysis. *Health Policy Plan*. 2014;29(6):784-794.
26. Muzammil M, Asmari DSA, Rethaiaa AS Al, Mutairi AS Al, Rashidi TH Al, Rasheedi HA Al, et al. Prevalence and perception of shisha smoking among university students: A cross-sectional study. *J Int Soc Prev Community Dent*. 2019;9(3):275–81.

27. Alqahtani RT, Moody J, Alhemodi NN, Alghamdi MS, Alhajhussein S. Peer and Social Correlates of Smoking among Saudi Youth. *Socius*. 2024;10:10.1177/23780231241286735.
28. Monshi SS, Wu J, Collins BN, Ibrahim JK. Youth susceptibility to tobacco use in the Gulf Cooperation Council Countries, 2001–2018. *Prev Med Rep*. 2022;26:101704.
29. Alwafi H, Naser AY, Alharbi R, Tawakkul S, Albayhie A, Alsaiari W, et al. Prevalence, safety, and role of nicotine pouches in smoking cessation among smokers and the public in Saudi Arabia. *Sci Rep*. 2025;15(1):32541.
30. Al-Qashoti MR, Aljassim R, Sherbash MAM, Alhussaini NWZ, Al-Jayyousi GF. Tobacco cessation programs and factors associated with their effectiveness in the Middle East: A systematic review. *Tob Induc Dis*. 2022;20:94.
31. Alshahrani NZ. Association between exposure to tobacco control measures and current nicotine use among adolescents in Saudi Arabia: Evidence from the 2022 global youth tobacco survey. *Prev Med Rep*. 2025; 59:102034.
32. Monshi SS, Arbaein TJ, Alanazi AM. Banning tobacco products sales to adolescents in the Gulf Cooperation Council countries. *East Mediterr Health J*. 2024;30(11):730-737.
33. Abu-Rmeileh NME, Khader YS, Abdul Rahim H, Mostafa A, Nakkash RT, Hamadeh RR, et al. Tobacco control in the Eastern Mediterranean region: implementation progress and persisting challenges. *Tob Control*. 2022;31(2):150-152.
34. Sultan Y, Salman Z, Alzaatreh M, Edilbi A, Alani R, Sultan I, et al. Smoking-Related Disease Impact in the Eastern Mediterranean Region: A Comprehensive Assessment Using Global Burden of Disease Data. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev*. 2024;25(2):495-505.
35. Abrams DB, Glasser AM, Pearson JL, Villanti AC, Collins LK, Niaura RS. Harm Minimization and Tobacco Control: Reframing Societal Views of Nicotine Use to Rapidly Save Lives. *Annu Rev Public Health*. 2018; 39:193-213.
36. Vupputuri S, Hajat C, Al-Houqani M, Osman O, Sreedharan J, Ali R, et al. Midwakh/dokha tobacco use in the Middle East: Much to learn. *Tob Control*. 2016;25(2):236–41.
37. Dalibalta S, Makhlof Z, Rabah L, Samara F, Elsayed Y. A literature review addressing midwakh and e-cigarette use in the Gulf region. *J Egypt Public Health Assoc*. 2023; 98:28.
38. Al Ghobain M; Ahmed AE; Abdrabalnabi Z; Mutairi W; Khathaami AA. Prevalence of and attitudes to waterpipe smoking among Saudi Arabian physicians. *East Mediterr Health J*. 2018;24(3):277–282.
39. Saudi Arabia health news. [Midwakh pipe smoking posing 'significant' health problems in UAE, scientists find | EurekAlert!](#) Last Accessed 06 March 2026.

40. Maziak W, Osibogun O, Asfar T. Waterpipe smoking: the pressing need for risk communication. *Expert Rev Respir Med.* 2019;13(11):1109-1119.
41. Asfar T, Chehab S, Schmidt M, Ward KD, Maziak W, Nakkash R. "Scary and Effective, Definitely Pushes Me to Quit Smoking": Developing Waterpipe Pictorial Health Warnings Targeting Young Adults in Lebanon. *Nicotine Tob Res.* 2022;24(9):1458-1468.
42. Saddik B. Tradition to Concern: Health Risks and Nicotine Dependence of Midwakh Use in Young Males in the UAE. *Eur J Public Health.* 2024;34(suppl 3):ckae144.397.
43. Akl EA, Gunukula SK, Aleem S, Obeid R, Jaoude PA, Honeine R. The prevalence of waterpipe tobacco smoking among the general and specific populations: a systematic review. *BMC Public Health.* 2011; 11:244.
44. Romani M, Jawhar S, Shalak M, Antoun J. Waterpipe smoking cessation: Knowledge, barriers, and practices of primary care physicians- A questionnaire-based cross-sectional study. *BMC Fam Pract.* 2020; 21(1):17
45. El-Awaisi A, Awaisu A, Saffouh M, Hajj E, Alemrayat B, Al-Jayyousi G, et al. Delivering Tobacco Cessation Content in the Middle East Through Interprofessional Learning. *J Interprof Care.* 2017; 31(6):767-770.
46. El Hajj MS, Awaisu A, Saleh RA, Al Hamad NM, Kheir N, Zeenny RM, et al. Tobacco-related education in schools of pharmacy in the Middle East: A multinational cross-sectional study. *Nicotine Tob Res.* 2018; 20(5):561–7.
47. Huang J, Feng B, Weaver SR, Pechacek TF, Slovic P, Eriksen MP. Changing Perceptions of Harm of e-Cigarette vs Cigarette Use among Adults in 2 US National Surveys from 2012 to 2017. *JAMA Netw Open.* 2019; 2(3): e191047.
48. Hiilamo H, Glantz S. Global Implementation of Tobacco Demand Reduction Measures Specified in Framework Convention on Tobacco Control. *Nicotine Tob Res.* 2022; 24(4):503-510.
49. Monshi SS, Ibrahim J. Implementation of tobacco control measures in the Gulf Cooperation Council countries, 2008–2020. *Subst Abuse Treat Prev Policy.* 2021; 16(1):82.
50. Hajat C, Stein E, Ramstrom L, Shantikumar S, Polosa R. The health impact of smokeless tobacco products: a systematic review. *Harm Reduct J.* 2021; 18(1):123.
51. Al-Houqani M, Ali R, Hajat C. Tobacco smoking using Midwakh is an emerging health problem - evidence from a large cross-sectional survey in the United Arab Emirates. *PLoS One.* 2012; 7(6):e39189.
52. Liakoni E, Christen SE, Benowitz NL. E-cigarettes, synthetic nicotine, heated-tobacco and smokeless nicotine delivery products: the nicotine landscape beyond combustible cigarettes. *Swiss Med Wkly.* 2024; 154:w30265.
53. Cheng HG, Noggle B, Flora JW. Comparative disease risks associated with cigarette smoking and use of moist smokeless tobacco and snus: an umbrella review of

- epidemiological evidence from the United States and Western Europe. *BMC Public Health*. 2025;25(1):3765.
54. Afolabi SO, Olaoye SO, Nyamgee A, Njan AA. Comparative effects of alternate tobacco products and traditional tobacco smoking on various organ/systems: A guide to regulators and health policy makers. *Toxicol Rep*. 2025; 15:102100.
 55. Al-Otaibi HM, Althobiani MA. Nicotine pouches: a narrative review of the existing literature. *Front Public Health*. 2025; 13:1641308.
 56. Alkharaan H, Alrubayyi A, Kariri M, et al. Investigating oral nicotine pouch use among adults in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia: prevalence, awareness, susceptibility, and associated symptoms. *Front Public Health*. 2025; 13:1607656.
 57. Azzopardi D, Liu C, Murphy J. Chemical characterization of tobacco-free "modern" oral nicotine pouches and their position on the toxicant and risk continuums. *Drug Chem Toxicol*. 2022; 45(5):2246-2254.
 58. Smokefree Sweden-2025. <https://smokefreesweden.org/2025/03/25/policysmoke-free/> Last Accessed 06 March 2026.